

AN ANALYSIS ON MARKETING STRATEGIES FOR PROMOTING ORGANIC FOOD PRODUCTS

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Abstract : The purpose of this research paper is to present a comprehensive analysis of the marketing techniques used to promote organic food items. With consumers favoring more ecologically friendly and health-conscious products, the organic food sector is leading this revolutionary trend. This research aims to reveal the complex dynamics of effective marketing techniques in the organic food business by thoroughly examining and analyzing the literature, industry reports, and case studies. The research investigates the most recent developments, consumer trends, and creative strategies that support the expansion and long-term viability of organic food items on the market today. This study aims to highlight the combination of authenticity, transparency, and eco-consciousness to provide useful information for companies and marketers navigating the challenging terrain of organic food product promotion.

Key Words-Organic food marketing, Consumer trends, Effective marketing strategies, Sustainability marketing.

Introduction

Around the world, organic food is getting more and more popular. As people grow more worried about their health, the health of the environment, and global effects, they are also becoming more aware of food safety and environmental issues. Organic food products are grown without chemicals, fertilisers, pesticides, or other artificial enhancers. Consumers prefer organic foods because of their nutritional content, flavour, accessibility, affordability, freshness, attractiveness, pricing, etc. Growing consumer interest, retailers who actively encourage growth, product advertisements, an acceleration in the variety and range of products available to farmers, and various forms of support for production conversion have all been major factors in developing the organic sector. This helps commercial businesses promote organic products more effectively and improves organic farming. Government regulations on consumer education about the benefits of organic food are also advantageous. To protect the environment, consumers are urged to adopt ecologically friendly practices, such as eating organic food (Chen and Peng, 2012). This project aims to replace artificial processes with more sustainable ones to address the increasing demand for organic commodities. Its tenets are based on regional realities, such as the necessity for producers and farmers to have easy access to resources, including land, financing, support from the government, and regional markets (Schille et al., 2020). Using locally obtained components, the lack of artificial chemicals, and the promotion of human health and ecological balance set organic goods apart (Dhaoui et al., 2020). Vukasovic (2016) asserts that customers are more likely to buy organic fruits and vegetables than organic meat. It is important to remember that non-vegetarian, organic poultry, eggs, meat, and dairy products come from animals that were not given antibiotics or growth hormones.

Organic food is produced on farms without using biotechnology, artificial fertilisers, or pesticides (USDA, 2000). In this context, we follow our trip as it reveals the layers of marketing techniques that push organic food items to the forefront of consumers' conscious choices. This study aims to provide a comprehensive knowledge of the complex factors that support effective marketing campaigns in organic food products, ranging from the development of the organic food sector to the subtleties of consumer decision-making. Come along with us as we explore influencer relationships, digital marketing, sustainability programmes, and other areas as we try to figure out how to maximise market share while positively impacting a healthy and sustainable future.

Marketing strategies

Retailers use digital marketing methods to promote their businesses in today's digitally connected environment. These cutting-edge, innovative digital marketing techniques are distinct in every way. Organic shops employ a variety of tactics, such as email marketing, social media marketing, video promotion, on- and off-page optimisation, and technology, to reach their target audience directly. Direct channels, such as CSAs, grocery stores, or restaurant sales, can be added as the company expands. Wholesale and direct sales channels for certain crops or a portion of a crop may be combined. Usually, the objective is to create a plan for selling every item they make. This may be accomplished through one or more marketing channels. A farm's company may expand to include more direct market outlets John Haff (2017). According to Saniya Syed et al. (2021) Marketing strategies focusing on human connections is crucial for obtaining product feedback as well. Organise farm tours in

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collaboration with local organisations, schools, and associations. Take advantage of the media's attention to publish on cutting-edge topics.

Base your marketing plan on your understanding of customer behaviour and culture. Utilise the logo to promote the brand and the business. Consider the domestic and international markets.

Advantages of Marketing Strategies

- Help vendors of organic products establish online connections with customers
- increases the conversion rates for retailers of organic food
- helps organic product vendors cut costs associated with pointless advertising
- Facilitates instantaneous client support
- links the vendor of organic products with mobile customers
- increases revenue
- increases the return on investment for organic product vendors' campaigns
- Maintains Organic Product Vendors Competitive
- helps the vendor of organic products to compete with big businesses

Marketing channels for Organic Products

Review of Literature

Sukanya Barua et al (2023) Although consumers have low to medium levels of awareness, this study found that opinions towards organic food products are generally favorable. Society can benefit from sporadic awareness campaigns and capacity-building initiatives about various organic food issues in educational institutions, residential communities, and through the media. **Sonali Malewar et al. (2023)** According to this study, convenience, nutrient content, and consumer self-identification all have an impact on whether organic food will be consumed. The sensory appeal elements also have little impact on consumers' intention to buy despite their health consciousness. **Shahnaj Akter et al (2023)** The healthy qualities of foods with an eco-label, as well as the communication of knowledge about climate change, have a significant impact on the level of Purchase Intention

in an Emerging of intake of organic foods, in part because there is a significantly lower price level difference between organic food products and traditional foods. **Dinkar Joshi et al (2023)** The study demonstrates that the reach of organic products, their price, and their quality are the three main variables influencing consumer behavior. Businesses should put their efforts into making organic products available at a price that is prudent for a lot of consumers and, as a result, has sufficient quality.

Shampy Kamboj et al (2023) Based to the study, consumer intention to purchase organic food products is affected and predicted by consumer understanding of organic food, health advantages, convenience, availability, quality, and social norms. **Anamika Chaturvedi et al (2022)** The study demonstrates that consumers' preferences for organic food products take into account lifestyle diseases like obesity and heart disease as well as rising income and consumer education levels. This creates a significant opportunity for marketers to grow their organic food businesses.

SherinNachiya and Karthikheyam (2022) In accordance to the outcomes, there is demand for organic farming in the future and organic food could see a rise in popularity. Because some pollutions intensify health issues and because eating organic food is a cure-all for life, it is essential for health concerns. **Udgam Mishra (2022)** This study revealed information regarding the necessity of purchasing organic food goods and the need for various marketing initiatives that demonstrate the quality of the foods being sold. Consumers can be persuaded by retailers using quality check certification.

Disha Bagade (2021) The survey indicates that consumers will be more inclined to buy organic goods if given more information, a wider range of options, timely availability, and a reasonable pricing. The government should also assist the producers and marketing bodies in putting into action and enhancing their production and marketing activities to seize the market for organic products. **Nidhi Sharma and Shweta Bhatia (2021)** This study finds that customer opinions on organic food products are directly influenced by demographic factors such health consciousness, environmental concern, subjective norms, and willingness to pay. Considering environmental protection also increases their commercial appeal.

Suryatapa Das et al (2020) This study examines how eating organic food ensures food safety from farm to plate, the manner in which organic farming preserves environmental integrity and soil health, and the way it fosters consumer health, ecological health, and economic growth by generating income across the board. **Dasari Panduranga Rao (2020)** The results of this study suggested that health awareness, ecological consciousness, and animal welfare concerns are major drivers of organic food consumption, and that these drivers have a beneficial impact on consumers' intentions to buy and actual purchases of organic food products. **N Savithri and B Lavanya (2019)** this research shows that customers' overall decision to buy organic food products is largely influenced by the two aspects of flavor and chemical freedom. Additionally, it advises marketers to use a single strategy in their advertising campaigns that focuses

solely on health advantages. **R Ayswarya and S Vasanthi (2018)** The author acknowledged that customers' impression of organic products is related to their environmental friendliness and health benefits, and has demonstrated favorable shopping habits for organic food items. By providing information on the advantages of the products, this research suggests growing the market for these goods. **Chaitra Bharat and H M Chandrashekar (2018)** says all consumer groups should be made aware of the need for organic food certification, and the government should support farmers by offering subsidies for the certification's high cost.

IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

The importance of a study on "An Analysis on Marketing Strategies for Promoting Organic Food Products" lies in its potential to contribute valuable insights to various stakeholders, including businesses, consumers, policymakers, and researchers. Here are several key reasons is important: health and wellness concerns, environmental sustainability, consumer bahviour insights, brand image and reputations etc...

OBJECTIVES

- To analyze the impact of socio-demographic variables (age, income education etc. on consumer preferences for organic foods.
- To explore the marketing strategies and benefits purchasing organic food products.

Hypotheses for the Research Objectives:

Objective 1: Impact of Socio-demographic Variables

- H1: There is a significant relationship between at least one socio-demographic variable (age, income, education etc.) and consumer preference for organic food products.

- H0: There is no significant relationship between any socio-demographic variable (age, income, education etc.) and consumer preference for organic food products.

Objective 2: Marketing Strategies and Benefits

- H1: Consumers who are exposed to marketing strategies emphasizing health benefits will have a higher purchase intention for organic food compared to those who are not.
- H0: There is no significant difference in purchase intention for organic food products between consumers exposed to marketing strategies and those who are not.

Research Methodology

Give a brief outline of the research, focusing on analyzing marketing techniques for promoting organic food goods in the Bengaluru region. Emphasize the need of researching this particular situation.

To gain a thorough understanding of marketing tactics, use a mixed-methods strategy that combines qualitative and quantitative research techniques. Employ questionnaires and interviews to gather information.

Sampling method

Identify the target demographic as Bengaluru residents who purchase organic food items. To make sure that different demographic groups are represented, use convenient sampling. Establish inclusion criteria based on the consumption patterns of organic food.

Data Collection Tools and Methods

To collect quantitative data on customer preferences and the efficacy of marketing efforts, use a systematic survey questionnaire. For qualitative insights, conduct semi-structured interviews with important industry participants, including organic farmers, merchants, and marketing experts. Describe the participant recruiting method, with a focus on interacting with online communities, supermarkets, and local organic markets. Give precise instructions on how the survey will be distributed, when it will be collected, and when interviews will take place. Determine factors including customer perceptions, awareness, and preferences about food goods that are organic. Operationalize these characteristics with Likert scales and open-ended questions. Add factors relating to marketing, such as price strategy, branding, and promotional activities.

Data Analysis

Quantify survey responses using statistical analyses such as inferential tests and descriptive statistics. Apply theme analysis to qualitative interview data to find trends and patterns in marketing tactics.

Table No-1: Demographical Analysis

Particulars	Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Female	114	52.8
	Male	102	47.2
	Total	216	100.0
Generation Level	Generation-X	146	67.6
	Generation-Y	55	25.5
	Generation-Z	15	6.9
	Total	216	100.0
Monthly Income	Upto Rs 15000	10	4.6
	Rs 15001-30000	14	6.5
	Rs 30001-45000	16	7.4
	Rs 45001-60000	42	19.4
	Rs Above 60000	134	62.0
	Total	216	100.0

Education	SSLC	1	0.50
	HSC/PUC	10	4.6
	DIPLOMA	2	0.9
	UG	96	44.4
	PG	94	43.5
	Doctorate/ Professional	13	6.0
	TOTAL	216	100.0
Occupation	Homemaker	129	59.7
	Private Employee	72	33.3
	Government Employee	15	7.0
	Total	216	100.0

The above table reveals the demographics of organic food product users in Bengaluru city. More than half (52.8%) of the respondents are female who has involved in this study, and little above two-third (67.6%) of the respondents are belonging into Generation X (birth duration of 1963-1980) and around 62% of the respondents are earning their monthly income more than Rs 60000, most of the respondents are done the under graduation level and 59.7% respondents occupations is home maker.

Table No-2; Using Marketing Strategy

Particular	No. of. Respondents	Percentage
Traditional Marketing	146	67.6
Digital Marketing	55	25.5
Both	15	6.9
Total	216	100.0

Table No-3: Traditional Marketing Strategy

S.No	Particulars		Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Occasionally	Always	Total	Mean	Std. Dev
1	Community Supported Agriculture (CSA)	Nos	1	8	17	65	125	216	4.41	0.825
		%	0.5	3.7	7.9	30.1	57.9	100		
2	Farmer's Market	Nos	1	6	13	41	155	216	4.59	0.767
		%	0.5	2.8	6	19	71.8	100		
3	Farm Stands	Nos	5	11	28	55	117	216	4.24	1.015
		%	2.3	5.1	13	25.5	54.2	100		
4	Restaurants	Nos	1	11	32	56	116	216	4.27	0.927
		%	0.5	5.1	14.8	25.9	53.7	100		
5	Word-up-mouth	Nos	2	6	26	47	135	216	4.42	0.875
		%	0.9	2.8	12	21.8	62.5	100		

Table No-4

Group Statistics					
	Age	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Tele Advertising	Female	114	4.53	.696	.058
	Male	102	4.42	.854	.115
E-Mail Marketing	Female	114	4.59	.701	.058
	Male	102	4.45	.878	.118
Social Media Marketing	Female	114	4.42	.803	.066
	Male	102	4.38	.871	.117
SEO marketing	Female	114	4.32	.828	.069
	Male	102	4.44	.788	.106
Social Marketing	Female	114	4.18	.966	.080
	Male	102	4.11	1.031	.139
Mobile Marketing	Female	114	4.41	.785	.065
	Male	102	4.44	.788	.106

Table No-5

Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means				
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
Tele Advertising	Equal variances	2.095	0.149	0.988	199	0.324	0.116	0.117
	Not Equal variances			0.901	82.519	0.37	0.116	0.129
E-Mail Marketing	Equal variances	4.458	0.036	1.128	199	0.261	0.134	0.119
	Not Equal variances			1.02	81.332	0.311	0.134	0.132
Social Media Marketing	Equal variances	0.7	0.404	0.277	199	0.782	0.036	0.13
	Not Equal variances			0.267	90.648	0.79	0.036	0.135
SEO marketing	Equal variances	0.319	0.573	-0.94	199	0.35	-0.121	0.129
	Not Equal variances			-0.96	101.76	0.34	-0.121	0.126
Social Marketing	Equal variances	0.057	0.811	0.443	199	0.658	0.069	0.156
	Not Equal variances			0.43	91.934	0.668	0.069	0.16

Mobile Marketing	Equal variances	0.011	0.917	-0.2	199	0.838	-0.025	0.124
	Not Equal variances			-0.2	96.88	0.839	-0.025	0.125

The Levene's test shows significant difference in the variances (as $p > 0.05$), it becomes necessary to use the equal variance t test and hence the corresponding p values for the same. In case significant difference in the variances (as $p < 0.05$), it becomes necessary to use the unequal variance t test and hence the corresponding p values for the same. It can be interpreted that the Levene's test for the equality of variance indicate that the variances of male and female respondent are equal to the digital marketing strategies of organic food products; specifically E-mail marketing $p > 0.05$ (p values are 0.261 and 0.311 respectively). Hence it evident that null hypothesis are accepted.

Table No-6

Ranks	
Marketing Strategies	Mean Rank
Community Supported Agriculture	6.15
Farmer's Market	6.86
Farm Stands	5.66
Restaurants	5.60
Word-up-mouth	6.24
Tele Advertising	6.29
Social Media Marketing	6.47
E-Mail Marketing	5.89
SEO Marketing	5.72
Social Marketing	5.12
Mobile Marketing	5.99

According to the mean rank for sources of information; Farmer's market, social media marketing, tele advertising, word-up-mouth, community supported agriculture, mobile marketing, E-mail marketing, SEO marketing, Farm stands, Restaurants, and social marketing are in the order. Thus farmer's market plays an important role for the organic food products.

Table No-7

Test Statistics ^a	
N	216
Chi-Square	88.074
df	10
Asymp. Sig.	0.000
a. Friedman Test	

Friedman test has been administered to determine whether participants have a differential rank order preference for the different source of marketing strategy. Results of these analysis indicate differential rank order preference for the different source of information $\chi^2 = 88.074$, $p < 0.05$, hence it is concluded that there is a significant difference between marketing strategies for the organic products.

Conclusions

Organic food is becoming increasingly popular worldwide due to growing concerns about food safety, environmental sustainability, and health. Organic products appeal more to consumers because of their flavour, freshness, accessibility, affordability, and nutritional value. The study highlights the critical role that several stakeholders—consumers, retailers, and governmental regulations—play in supporting the expansion of the organic industry. To fulfil the growing demand for organic goods, the study highlights the need to substitute sustainable procedures for artificial ones. It acknowledges the reality of the local area, including the requirement for producers and farmers to have easy access to resources, government assistance, and local markets. The research examines various marketing strategies, from conventional techniques like word-of-mouth and Community

Supported Agriculture (CSA) to modern digital strategies, including email marketing, social media marketing, and SEO. The many channels facilitate communication with various customer categories, which enhances the overall efficacy of organic marketing initiatives. Additionally, the study explores the benefits of these marketing techniques, emphasising how they help create online relationships with clients, boost conversion rates, reduce wasteful advertising expenses, offer immediate customer service, and stay competitive in the industry.

Future Directions of the study

Future research may concentrate on how consumer awareness efforts affect consumers' preferences for organic food products. It would be beneficial to examine how well educational programmes work to change consumer behaviour and increase the use of organic foods.

- Examine the efficacy of marketing tactics in various locales and societies. Comprehending the ways in which cultural subtleties influence consumers' opinions and inclinations towards organic products may assist organisations in customising their strategies for varied markets.
- Examine new sustainable farming methods in organic agriculture and how they can affect marketing plans. Examining developments in sustainable supply chains, farm-to-table programmes, and environmentally friendly packaging might raise the allure of organic goods.
- To monitor changes in customer behaviour over time, conduct longitudinal research. Businesses may create flexible and future-proof marketing strategies by having a thorough understanding of the elements driving the organic sector's continuous expansion and the evolution of consumer preferences.

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